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THE APENNINE SIBYL

A MYSTERY AND A LEGEND

ANTOINE DE LA SALE AND THE MAGICAL BRIDGE CONCEALED BENEATH MOUNT SIBYL¹

1. The true story of a literary tradition

When Antoine de La Sale, in his *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*, reported the mysterious, riveting tales about what lies within the inner recesses of Mount Sibyl, in the cave he was visiting in year 1420, accompanied by the peasants of Montemonaco, he wrote of that blood-curdling bridge that daring visitors would stumble upon when creeping in the bowels of the mountain:

«Then you find a bridge, made of some unknown material, but it is said to be less than a single foot wide and it seems to be extending far ahead. Below the bridge, a ghastly, precipitating abyss [...] Yet as soon as you put both feet on the bridge, it becomes large enough; and the more you step ahead, the more it widens and the abyss becomes shallower» [in the original French text: «Lors trouve-l'on ung pont, que on ne scet de quoy il est, mais est advis qu'il n'est mie ung pied de large et semble estre moult long. Dessoubz ce pont, a très grant et hydeux abisme de parfondeur [...] Mais aussitost que on a les deux pieds sur le pont, il est assez large; et tant va on plus avant et plus est large et moins creux»].

At a first glance, this magical bridge is a much odd, unconventional piece of narration: it is a wondrous token of the Sibyl's fairy kingdom, it gives the creeps to the readers, it adds a lot to the final effect that de La Sale, a

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smart courtier, eager to please his audience, intended to impart to his narrative.

But was de La Sale sincere, original and authentic in this part of his account?

No, he wasn't. And the "Apennine Sibyl - A Mystery and a Legend" is proud to provide a full demonstration of it.

We saw already that the magical bridge was present in a different, earlier narrative as well: *Huon d'Auvergne*, a thirteenth-century epic poem - which we saw had some close links with our Apennine Sibyl legend.

In *Huon d'Auvergne*, the enchanted bridge was described as follows:

«I will tell you how cruel was that bridge: - Its top side is as sharp as an arrow - And it cleaves more easily than a sword [...] then they ventured across the bridge with small steps - so that they safely reached the far edge» [in the original French-Italian text: «La crudelitate del ponte ve voio contere: - Desovra è agudo como quarel d'açere - E pluy ca spada ello taia volentiere [...] Po se meteno su per lo ponte a pas petis - Tanto che sono oltro el pont sulla ris»].

A bridge, as sharp as a blade, as narrow as a razor: but if your faith in God is strong, it becomes larger and larger, and you are safely through. If you don't believe, you fall.

An ordeal which puts your soul to the ultimate test.

Where does this bridge comes from? If it is found in both *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* and *Huon d'Auvergne*, does it come from some earlier literary ancestor?

Actually, the bridge comes straight out from the twelfth century (and actually - as we will see later on - from even earlier). It comes from the *Tractatus de Purgatorio Sancti Patricii*, from the tale of the knight Owain confronting the demons who want to snatch his soul:

«A bridge crossed the river [covered with roaring, fiendish flames], which showed three impossible features, to the utter terror of those who had to get through: the first was that it was slippery, so that even if it had been wide enough, no one would be able to set its foot firmly onto it; furthermore, it was so narrow and frail that nobody would dare to stand nor tread on it; third, it was so tall over a river down below that utterly frightful was the vision of the abyss [...] However the knight, who trusted in Jesus [...] bravely entered the bridge and began to walk on it, without sensing nothing slippery under his feet [...] and finding the bridge wider and wider; and after a little while so grew the width of the bridge, that ahead of him it was as large as a public street, and eleven wagons travelling at the same time would enjoy enough space [...] He saw that the broadness of the bridge was growing so much that scarcely he could now see the two sides of it».

[In the original Latin text: «Pons vero protendebatur ultra flumen [sulphurei incendii flamma copertum], in quo tria quasi impossibilia et transeuntibus valde formidanda videbantur, unum quod ita lubricus erat, ut etiam si latus fuerit, nullus vel vix aliquis in eo pedem figere posset; alterum quod tam strictus et gracilis erat, ut nullus in eo stare vel ambulare valeret; tertium quod tam altus erat, et a flumine remotus ut horrendum esset deorsum aspicere [...] Sed miles Christi fidelis [...] pontem audacter ingressus, coepit pedetentium incedere, nihilque lubrici sub pedibus sentiens [...] eo spatiosorem invenit pontem; et ecce post paululum tanta crevit pontis latitudo, ut publicae viae amplitudinem prae se ferret, et undecim carra sibi obvianta posset excipere [...] vidit latitudinem pontis in tantum excrescere, ut vix ex utraque parte ejus fines posset aspicere»].

Thus, when the experienced author and courtier Antoine de La Sale tells his readers of a magical bridge that would be located under Mount Sibyl, in Italy, he's just using the tools of a writer to impart more flavour to his narrative: he draws an awe-inspiring bridge from an earlier tradition - that of the Purgatory of St. Patrick, featuring a similar cave, a subterranean population of demons, and a similar knightly adventure - and puts it in his writer's cauldron, with a view to fully absorb his audience's attention.

Just a literary trick. There are no such bridges under Mount Sibyl. Nor they have ever been.

And that bridge is even more antique than the twelfth-century account which is retrieved in the *Tractatus de Purgatorio Sancti Patricii*.

Let's take the *Vision of St. Adamnán*: it's an eleventh-century account written in the *Lebor na hUidre*, the Book of the Dun Cow, an ancient Irish manuscript (MS 23 E 25, preserved at the Royal Irish Academy in Dublin). It reports a vision by St. Adamnán, the abbot of the great monastery of Iona in the seventh century A.D. Just like Owain, he is transported as far as Hell, and the following is what he finds there:

«An enormous bridge spans the glen, reaching from one bank to the other [...] One company finds the bridge to be of ample width, from beginning to the end, until they win across the fiery glen, safe and sound, fearless and undismayed. The second company, when entering upon it, finds it narrow at first, but broad afterwards [...] But for the last company the bridge is broad at first, but strait and narrow thereafter, until they fall from the midst of it into that same persilous glen, into the throats of those eight red-hot serpents. [...] Now the folk to whom that path was easy were the chaste, the penitent, the diligent [...] They, however, to whom this way was broad at first, but strait thereafter, were sinners».

Fig. 1 - The excerpt on the test-bridge from the *Vision of St. Adamnán* contained in the *Book of the Dun Cow* manuscript, with on its top-right side the ancient Irish word 'drocher' for 'bridge'

[In the original Irish text: «Drocher dérmár dan darsin n-glend...»]

This is nothing else but Antoine de La Sale's bridge! The same changing narrowness and width, the same trial for pure, unblemished souls. But in the *Vision of St. Adamnán*, just like in *The Purgatory of St. Patrick*, the bridge is encountered during a travel into the other world, while Antoine de La Sale has adapted it to a travel into a magical world set beneath a specific mountain, Mount Sibyl.

Are the listed ones the only mentions we have in ancient manuscripts about the bridge? Not at all.

In the Western world, the earliest mention of such a test bridge is found in a work by Pope St. Gregory I the Great, who lived in the sixth century A.D. In his *Dialogues* (Book IV, Chapter XXXVI) the first instance of an otherworldly vision is portrayed. Again, a soldier is paying a visit to the afterlife, and a perilous bridge is depicted:

«He [the soldier] said [...] that there was a bridge, under which a black river was flowing, which was sending out vapours of foggy, unbearable stench. After the bridge, a charming grassland full of greenery was visible [...] In that bridge was actually a trial: everybody who attempted to cross with a faulty soul would slip and fall in the gloomy, stinky waters; the righteous, with an unblemished soul, would safely enter the bridge and freely cross it to reach the delightful vision. [...] He saw the just crossing over a bridge to a beautiful place, because the path that leads to eternal life is extremely narrow».

[In the original Latin text: «Aiebat [miles] enim [...] quia pons erat, sub quo niger atque caliginosus foetoris intolerabilis nebulam exhalans fluvius decurrebat. Transacto autem ponte, amoena erant prata atque virentia [...] Haec vero erat in praedicto ponte probatio ut quisquis per eum vellet injustorum transire, in tenebrosam foetentemque fluvium laberetur: justi vero quibus culpa non obsisteret, securo per eum gressu ac libero ad loca amoena pervenirent. [...] Per pontem quippe ad amoena loca transire justos aspexit: Quia angusta valde est semita quae ducit ad vitam».]

Again, the very same bridge. The same bridge that Antoine de La Sale used in his *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*.

Because, as Carol Zaleski writes in her most informed essay *Otherworld Journeys: Accounts of Near-Death Experience in Medieval and Modern Times*, «from the time of Gregory the Great until at least the fifteenth century, the test-bridge is a recurrent feature of Western vision literature».

We find the test-bridge almost everywhere, with its ever-changing narrowness, in a number of monastic texts, all describing the journey of a mortal man into the purgatorial otherworld, like the *Vision of Alberic* (twelfth century), the *Vision of Tnugdalus* (another twelfth century text), the *Vision of Sunniulf*, and then the *Vision of Ezra*. All the bridges in them are as narrow as the one contained - as alleged by Antoine de La Sale - in the bowels of Mount Sibyl, and so magical that they widen as you pass with unblemished faith, like the bridge of Tnugdalus shown in the miniature taken from a fifteenth-century manuscript.

Fig. 2 - A miniature from a *Les Visions du chevalier Tondal*, a French manuscripted version of the *Vision of Tnugdalus* dating to 1475 and preserved at the Getty Museum)

So, what can we say about the Mount Sibyl's bridge reported by Antoine de La Sale?

We can say one important thing, that will lead us to conclusions of the most fundamental momentum.

Not only there is no such bridge under Mount Sibyl (and this sentence may even be considered as trite), but, furthermore, the bridge is not part of the original core of the Apennine Sibyl's legend.

The bridge was added by Antoine de La Sale in his work to confer more spice to his narrative, using literary models he knew well, as they were part of a most renowned literary tradition spanning through Europe across a thousand years, throughout the Middle Ages. A bridge for testing the purity of soul: a powerful, visionary image that has been part of the Christian culture for centuries, as shown in an impressive fresco on “The Last Judgment” in the church of St. Maria in Piano, at Loreto Aprutino (Italy), with his astounding “test bridge as thin as a single hair”.

Fig. 3 - "The Last Judgment", fresco from the church of St. Maria in Piano, Loreto Aprutino (Italy) - Detail of the bridge "as thin as a single hair"

A bridge that actually comes to us from far, far away: its ultimate origin lies centuries before the advent of Jesus Christ, in ancient Iran, in the context of the antique Zoroastrian tradition of the “Chinvato Peretu”, the bridge of judgment: it narrows to a blade-edge, throwing sinful human souls into the abyss. A horrifying boundary between mortal life, eternal life, and death.

2. A discovery in “*Guerrino the Wretch*” and a quote from “*Indiana Jones*”

In the preceding paragraph, we provided the full evidence that the magically narrow bridge mentioned by Antoine de la Sale in his *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* as belonging to the local lore of the Apennine Sibyl is a fake.

The bridge was taken by Antoine de la Sale from earlier accounts, namely from the antique tradition of the “test bridges” used for the judgment of souls in the afterlife world, as found in the *Tractatus de Purgatorio Sancti Patricii*, many *Visions* dating to the early Middle Ages, the *Dialogues* by Pope St. Gregory I the Great, and pre-Christian traditions like the Zoroastrian belief about the bridge called “Chinvato Peretu”.

But what about Andrea da Barberino and his *Guerrino the Wretch*?

We know that the other fundamental text which provides a narration on the Apennine Sibyl, together with the one by Antoine de la Sale, is the fifteenth-century romance *Guerrino the Wretch*: has Andrea da Barberino included any magically narrow bridge in its description of the Sibyl's cave and subterranean kingdom?

Incredibly enough, the answer is both no and yes.

In the chapters from CXLIII to CLV, where Andrea da Barberino tells the tale of Guerrino's adventurous stay in the hollows of the Sibyl's cave, no reference is ever made to any bridges, supposedly crossing the abysses lying within the cavern. Guerrino enters the cave with «flint, steel and tinder», he finds «ghastly cavities», he feels he has «entered a strange kind of labyrinth»: yet, down there, no bridges are present, not to mention magical bridges as narrow as a single foot.

So the bridge that was mentioned by Antoine de la Sale is not referred to by Andrea da Barberino. But is this the final truth?

No, because Andrea da Barberino actually does mention the enchanted bridge. Where? In the section of the romance that follows the account on the Sibyl's cave. A section entirely devoted to the Purgatory of St. Patrick.

When we stated that the whole legend of the Apennine Sibyl presents very close connections to the tale of the *Tractatus de Purgatorio Sancti Patricii*, we were absolutely on target: so much so that - at the very end of the section dedicated to the Sibyl in his *Guerrino the Wretch* - Andrea da Barberino sends his knight hero, Guerrino, right into the Purgatory of St. Patrick, in Ireland, as a penitence imparted to him by the Pope for having been at the forbidden court of the Apennine Sibyl:

«The Holy Father spoke to him: 'You are blessed' [...] and, as a penitence, he commanded to him, the way he had dared violate God's edict not to enter the abode of the Sibyl and visit the illusory idols, to go to the Purgatory of St. Patrick, which is under the rule of the Archbishop of Hibernia in the island called Irlanda» [in the original Italian text: «El santo padre li disse: 'tu sei benedetto' [...] e per penitenzia impose como lui havea havuto ardire contra el comandamento de la leze de dio de intrare dove stava la Sibilla et de andare a visitare li idoli [...] chusi volea che per comandamento lui andasse a lo purgatorio de santo Patritio el quale è sotto l'arcivescovo de Ibernica in l'isola dita Irlanda»].

So, there is actually a significantly close connection between the Apennine Sibyl and the Purgatory of St. Patrick, as we already saw when we considered Antoine de la Sale's magically narrow bridge.

Guerrino like Owain: from this point on (chapter CLXII), Andrea da Barberino's narration follows the steps of the ancient Irish tradition, with Guerrino travelling as far as «the island of St. Patrick where the Purgatory stands», with the hero then ushered into «a huge cavern which proceeded under the ground». In the Purgatory, Guerrino beholds - as in all medieval *Visions* - the unbearable tortures suffered by the souls of the damned.

And then, in chapter CLXX, he encounters the bridge we well know:

«... and immediately he was standing on a bridge that crossed the marsh from one side to the other over a large river. And it seemed to him that the bridge was so narrow that nobody could have put one foot ahead of the other. He turned to get back but he could not see the bridge beneath his own eyes. And he saw countless jaws of big snakes and dragons, and it was as if they were waiting for him to fall down. Guerrino had never been so scared as in this predicament. And all the way along the bridge he feared he

would fall. And actually he was about to fall: but he called on the Holy Name, and by His mercy the bridge swell to a huge width. And he could go through this perilous passage» (see excerpt in figure).

[In the original Italian text: «... e subito fu drito sopra uno ponte che trapassava questo lagune da uno lato al altro sopra uno grande fiume. E parevali questo ponte tanto sottile, che uno piede avanti l'altro non li poteva stare. Lui se volse per tornare e non vide el ponte abasso gli ochi. E vide infinite bocche de grandi serpenti, e dragoni, e pareva che aspetassero che lui cadesse. Anchora non havea avuto Guerino maggior paura che questa. E tutta via li pareva de cadere. E pure saria caduto: ma chiamò el santo nome, e per la soa misericordia el ponte se li fece largissimo. E passò de là da questo fortunoso passo»].

That's the news: the magical bridge - the same one that Antoine de La Sale describes as standing in the inner recesses of the Sibyl's cave - is not placed by Andrea da Barberino in the section devoted to the Sibyl, as it is rather included by the writer in its 'original' legendary setting, i.e. that of the Purgatory of St. Patrick.

Literary inventions can be put anywhere, in the very spot where they are most needed by the author.

Fig. 4 - *Guerrino the Wretch*, the two different excerpts where the knight Guerrino encounters the same magical bridge

But here comes another remarkable surprise: as noted above, Andrea da Barberino did not include the magical bridge in his account about the Sibyl; yet, he liked the illustrious test-bridge so much that he mentioned it twice in the chapters dedicated to the visit of his hero Guerrino in the Purgatory of St. Patrick!

In fact, if we continue our reading of *Guerrino the Wretch*, we find the same bridge again in a subsequent portion of Guerrino's journey through the Purgatory (chapter CLXXXII):

«And he saw a river that was crossed by so thin and narrow a bridge that there was no small animal that would pass through it, because of his tiny width. He crossed himself and entrusted himself to God. he was taken [by the demons] and placed onto the middle of the bridge, where they left him, then they began to scream at him, and flung stones and shafts at him so that he was about to fall. And he turned to go back , and could see no bridge. So he looked at the bottom where the water was, and saw that it was full of hideous worms and snakes. The bridge was so thin that it was not possible to put one foot ahead of the other. He began to call the name of Jesus Christ from Nazareth, and the bridge started to get larger. As he spoke these words thrice, he began to sing 'Domine ne in furore tuo arguas me', and the bridge became even larger, and he was through» (see excerpt in figure).

[In the original Italian text: «e vide uno fiume cui atraverso li era uno ponte tanto sutile e stretto che lo non è si piccolo animale che havesse potuto passare, tanto era stretto. Lui se fece el segno de la santa croce e recomandose a dio. Fu preso [dai demoni] e posto suxo el mezo del ponte et ivi lo lassorono, e poi cominciarono a cridare et a zitarli pietre e pali per modo che el meschino fu per cadere. E lui se volse indietro per tornare indietro, e non vide ponte. Allora pose mente nel fundo de laqua, e lo vide pieno de vermini bruti e serpenti. El ponte era si stretto che uno pié inanti l'altro non li cadeva. Lui cominciò a chiamare iesu christo nazareno, e lo ponte si cominciò a largare. E dite queste parole tre volte, cominciò a cantare 'Domine ne in furore tuo arguas me', et el ponte se largava, e lui passò»].

Again, we find once more the test-bridge belonging to the antique tradition we have already explored, whose farthest origin dates back to pre-Christian Zoroastrianism.

What can we say at the very end of this ride across the centuries, in search of a very special bridge that plays a peculiar role in the Apennine Sibyl's legendary tale?

We have provided full demonstration of the following facts:

- 1) that the bridge described by Antoine de la Sale in his *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* is a mere literary invention that the author has passed off as a genuine tale relating to the Apennine Sibyl;
- 2) that the bridge does not belong to the original sibilline lore, being rather a superposition which was drawn - as a primary source - from the *Tractatus de Purgatorio Sancti Patricii*, which in turn is linked to many other medieval "Visions" and to even earlier oriental traditions concerning the judgment of souls in the afterlife;
- 3) that this is further confirmed by the fact that the romance *Guerrino the Wretch* does not mention the bridge in its sibilline section, but rather in its chapters relating to the Purgatory of St. Patrick, where the very same bridge is described not once, but twice.

The listed conclusions have never been presented to the public: no scholar has ever written anything about all this, so the whole is to be considered as a highly-valuable result obtained by the advanced research being conducted by "The Apennine Sibyl - A Mystery and a Legend".

We have obtained this remarkable result by following the literary history of a legendary, supernatural bridge, whose notion belongs to the deepest and most antique beliefs of mankind. A bridge that has made so long a journey into human history that it has travelled as far as our contemporary pop culture: a modern version of it, the invisible bridge, plays a magical role in the final sequences of Steven Spielberg's movie *Indiana Jones and the Last Crusade* (1989), with actor Harrison Ford putting hesitantly his foot on it to make what the movie script properly calls his personal "leap of faith" (see image). The soul of Indiana Jones, like the souls of Guerrino and Owain and the knights described by Antoine de la Sale, is put to test by the divine narrowness of the very same archetypal bridge.

Fig. 5 - An amazed Indiana Jones considers the magical bridge that will lead him into the room where the Holy Grail is preserved - from the final sequence of *Indiana Jones and the Last Crusade* (1989)

In a next article, we will see that a similar conclusion can be fully demonstrated when we take into consideration another magical device which appears in de la Sale's "The Paradise of Queen Sibyl": the ever-slammimg metal doors.

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